

PROPERTIES OF SMARANDACHE STAR TRIANGLE

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ABSTRACT: In [1] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION , as follows: Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \text{ could be expressed as the}$$

product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots$

$$, \alpha_r) = F'(N), \text{ where}$$

$$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

Also for the case

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \dots = \alpha_r = \dots = \alpha_n = 1$$

Let us denote

$$F(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, \dots) = F(1\#n)$$

← n - ones →

In [2] we define **The Generalized Smarandache Star**

Function as follows:

Smarandache Star Function

$$(1) \quad F'^*(N) = \sum_{d_r|N} F'(d_r) \quad \text{where } d_r|N$$

$$(2) \quad F'^{**}(N) = \sum_{d_r|N} F'^*(d_r)$$

d_r ranges over all the divisors of N .

If N is a square free number with n prime factors, let us denote

$$F'^{**}(N) = F'^{**}(1\#n)$$

Smarandache Generalised Star Function

$$(3) \quad F'^{n*}(N) = \sum_{d_r|N} F'^{(n-1)*}(d_r) \quad n > 1$$

and d_r ranges over all the divisors of N .

For simplicity we denote

$$F'(Np_1p_2 \dots p_n) = F'(N@1\#n), \text{ where}$$

$$(N, p_i) = 1 \text{ for } i = 1 \text{ to } n \text{ and each } p_i \text{ is a prime.}$$

$F'(N@1\#n)$ is nothing but the Smarandache factor partition of (a number N multiplied by n primes which are coprime to N).

In [2] I had derived a general result on the Smarandache Generalised Star Function. In the present note we define 'SMARANDACHE STAR TRIANGLE' (SST) and derive some properties of SST.

DISCUSSION:

DEFINITION : 'SMARANDACHE STAR TRIANGLE' (SST)

As established in [2]

$$a_{(n,m)} = (1/m!) \sum_{k=1}^m (-1)^{m-k} \cdot {}^m C_k \cdot k^n \text{ ----- (1)}$$

we have $a_{(n,n)} = a_{(n,1)} = 1$ and $a_{(n,m)} = 0$ for $m > n$. Now if one arranges these elements as follows

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} a_{(1,1)} & & & & & & \\ a_{(2,1)} & & a_{(2,2)} & & & & \\ a_{(3,1)} & & a_{(3,2)} & & a_{(3,3)} & & \\ \cdot & & & & & & \\ \cdot & & & & & & \\ \cdot & & & & & & \\ a_{(n,1)} & & a_{(n,2)} & \dots & a_{(n,n-1)} & a_{(n,n)} & \end{array}$$

we get the following triangle which we call as the ‘SMARANDACHE STAR TRIANGLE’ in which $a_{(r,m)}$ is the m^{th} element of the r^{th} row and is given by (A) above. It is to be noted here that the elements are the Stirling numbers of the first kind.

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} 1 & & & & & & \\ 1 & & 1 & & & & \\ 1 & & 3 & & 1 & & \\ 1 & & 7 & & 6 & & 1 \\ 1 & & 15 & & 25 & & 10 & & 1 \\ \dots & & & & & & & & \end{array}$$

Some propoerties of the SST.

(1) The elements of the first column and the last element of each row is unity.

(2) The elements of the second column are $2^{n-1} - 1$, where n is the row number.

(3) Sum of all the elements of the n^{th} row is the n^{th} Bell.

PROOF:

From theorem(3.1) of Ref; [2] we have

$$F'(N@1\#n) = F'(Np_1p_2 \dots p_n) = \sum_{m=0}^n a_{(n,m)} F'^{m*}(N)$$

if $N = 1$ we get $F'^{m*}(1) = F'^{(m-1)*}(1) = F'^{(m-2)*}(1) = \dots = F'(1) = 1$

hence

$$F'(p_1p_2 \dots p_n) = \sum_{r=0}^n a_{(n,m)}$$

(4)The elements of a row can be obtained by the following reduction formula

$$a_{(n+1,m+1)} = a_{(n,m)} + (m+1) \cdot a_{(n+1,m+1)}$$

instead of having to use the formula (4.5).

(5) If $N = p$ in theorem (3.1) Ref;[2] we get $F'^{m*}(p) = m + 1$. Hence

$$F'(pp_1p_2 \dots p_n) = \sum_{m=1}^n a_{(n,m)} F'^{m*}(N)$$

or
$$B_{n+1} = \sum_{m=1}^n (m+1) a_{(n,m)}$$

(6) Elements of second leading diagonal are triangular numbers in their natural order.

(7) If p is a prime, p divides all the elements of the p^{th} row except the 1st and the last, which are unity. This has been established in the following theorem.

THEOREM(1.1):

$$a_{(p,r)} \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \text{ if } p \text{ is a prime and } 1 < r < p$$

Proof:

$$a_{(p,r)} = (1/r!) \sum_{k=1}^m (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k^p$$

Also

$$a_{(p,r)} = (1/(r-1)!) \sum_{k=0}^{r-1} (-1)^{r-1-k} \cdot {}^{r-1} C_k \cdot (k+1)^{p-1}$$

$$a_{(p,r)} = (1/(r-1)!) \sum_{k=0}^{r-1} [(-1)^{r-1-k} \cdot {}^{r-1} C_k \cdot \{(k+1)^{p-1} - 1\}] +$$

$$(1/(r-1)!) \sum_{k=0}^{r-1} (-1)^{r-1-k} \cdot {}^{r-1} C_k$$

applying Fermat's little theorem, we get

$$a_{(p,r)} = \text{a multiple of } p + 0$$

$$\Rightarrow a_{(p,r)} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

COROLLARY: (1.1)

$$F(1\#p) \equiv 2 \pmod{p}$$

$$a_{(p,1)} = a_{(p,p)} = 1$$

$$F(1\#p) = \sum_{k=0}^p a_{(p,k)} = \sum_{k=2}^{p-1} a_{(p,k)} + 2$$

$$F(1\#p) \equiv 2 \pmod{p}$$

(8) The coefficient of the r^{th} term $b_{(n,r)}$ in the expansion of x^n as

$$x^n = b_{(n,1)} x + b_{(n,2)} x(x-1) + b_{(n,3)} x(x-1)(x-2) + \dots + b_{(n,r)} x P_r + \dots + b_{(n,n)} x P_n$$

is equal to $a_{(n,r)}$.

THEOREM(1.2): B_{3n+2} is even else B_k is odd.

From theorem (2.5) in REF. [1] we have

$$F'(Nq_1q_2) = F'^*(N) + F'^{**}(N) \text{ where } q_1 \text{ and } q_2 \text{ are prime.}$$

$$\text{and } (N, q_1) = (N, q_2) = 1$$

let $N = p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n$ then one can write

$$F'(p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n q_1 q_2) = F'^*(p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n) + F'^{**}(p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n)$$

$$\text{or } F(1\#(n+2)) = F(1\#(n+1)) + F^{**}(1\#n)$$

but

$$F^{**}(1\#n) = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r 2^{n-r} F(1\#r)$$

$$F^{**}(1\#n) = \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \{ {}^n C_r 2^{n-r} F(1\#r) \} + F(1\#n)$$

the first term is an even number say $= E$, This gives us

$$F(1\#(n+2)) - F(1\#(n+1)) - F(1\#n) = E, \text{ an even number. ---(1.1)}$$

Case- I: $F(1\#n)$ is even and $F(1\#(n+1))$ is also even $\Rightarrow$

$F(1\#(n+2))$ is even.

Case -II: $F(1\#n)$ is even and $F(1\#(n+1))$ is odd $\Rightarrow F(1\#(n+2))$ is odd.

again by (1.1) we get

$F(1\#(n+3)) - F(1\#(n+2)) - F(1\#(n+1)) = E$, $\Rightarrow F(1\#(n+3))$ is even. Finally we get

$F(1\#n)$ is even $\Leftrightarrow F(1\#(n+3))$ is even

we know that $F(1\#2) = 2 \Rightarrow F(1\#2), F(1\#5), F(1\#8), \dots$ are even

$\Rightarrow B_{3n+2}$ is even else B_k is odd

This completes the proof.

REFERENCES:

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